

A Simple Method for the Transformation of Steroidal Epoxides to Olefins

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5,6 α -Oxido-5 α -cholestane (1) and its 3 β -substituted analogues (2-4) on silver nitrate-neutral alumina surface were readily converted to cholest-5-ene (5) and its 3 β -substituted analogues (6-8) in 90-95% yield.

METHODS are reported in literature^{1,2} for the conversion of steroidal epoxides to the corresponding olefins with 8-40% yield. We have used a chromatographic column of 30% silver nitrate-neutral alumina³ for the transformation of 5,6 α -oxido-5 α -cholestane (1) and its 3 β -substituted analogues (2-4) to cholest-5-ene (5) and its 3 β -substituted-olefins (6-8) in 90-95% yield. The structures of these compounds were established on the basis of spectral studies.

Experimental

All melting points were observed on a Koflar apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were obtained with a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were run on a Varian A-60D instrument with Me₄Si as the internal standard. Thin layer chromatographic plates were coated with silica gel and sprayed with a aqueous 20% solution of perchloric acid. Petroleum ether refers to b.p. 60-80°. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

General procedure: Conversion of 5,6 α -oxido-5 α -cholestane (1) to cholest-5-ene (5): To a column of 30% silver nitrate (6 g) neutral alumina (20 g), 5,6 α -oxido-5 α -cholestane⁴ (1) (1.0 g) dissolved in dry ether (20 ml) was adsorbed and left the column at room temperature overnight. Elution with petroleum ether-ether (1:1) gave cholest-5-ene (5) as solid which was recrystallised from acetone (0.91 g), m.p. 94-95° (lit.⁶ m.p. 95°) (Found: C,

87.59; H, 12.43, C₂₇H₄₆ requires: C, 87.5; H, 12.4%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 5.28 mc (C6-H, $W_{1/2}$ 6 Hz), 1.17 (C10-CH₃), 0.70 (C13-CH₃), 0.94 and 0.84 (other methyl protons).

Under similar reaction conditions (same amounts of reactants were taken) epoxides 2⁴, 3⁷ and 4⁴ provided 6, 7 and 8: 3 β -hydroxycholest-5-ene (6; 0.92 g), m.p. 148-49° (lit.⁶ m.p. 149°) (Found: C, 83.93; H, 11.91. C₂₇H₄₆O requires: C, 83.9; H, 11.9%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 410 (br, 3-OH) and 1 625 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 3.21 (br, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3- α H), 5.26 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz, C6-H), 1.28 (C10-CH₃), 0.68 (C13-CH₃), 0.90 and 0.84 (other methyl protons); 3 β -chlorocholest-5-ene (7; 0.94 g), m.p. 95-6° (lit.⁶ m.p. 96-7°) (Found: C, 80.09; H, 11.12. C₂₇H₄₅Cl requires: C, 80.1; H, 11.1%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 625 (C=C) and 764 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ 3.58 (br, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 20 Hz, C3- α H), 5.29 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz, C6-H), 1.15 (C10-CH₃), 0.70 (C13-CH₃), 0.90 and 0.80 (other methyl protons); positive Beilstein test; 3 β -acetoxcholest-5-ene (8; 0.95 g), m.p. 115-16° (lit.⁶ m.p. 116°) (Found: C, 81.31; H, 11.21. C₂₉H₄₈O₂ requires: C, 81.3; H, 11.2%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 735 (CH₃COO), 1 625 (C=C), 1 460 and 1 050 cm⁻¹ (C-O); δ 4.45 (br, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3- α H), 5.30 (mc, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz, C6-H), 2.0 (s, CH₃COO), 1.16 (C10-CH₃), 0.70 (C13-CH₃), 0.98 and 0.83 (other methyl protons).

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